

PYTHAGOREAN CUBIC IDEAL IN SEMIGROUP

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ABSTRACT. In this paper, we introduce the notion of Pythagorean cubic ideal in semigroup. Also, we discuss some of their properties with examples.

1. INTRODUCTION

In 1965, Zadeh[8, 9] presented the idea of a fuzzy set. He also developed the notion of interval-valued fuzzy set in 1975 which is an expansion of the fuzzy set. A semigroup is an algebraic structure comprising of a non-empty set along with an affiliated binary operation. Atanassovo[2] presented the intuitionistic fuzzy set with certain properties. Atanassovo et al.[3] developed the idea of interval-valued intuitionistic fuzzy set. In 2012, Jun et al.[5] presented the idea of cubic set a combination of interval-valued fuzzy set and fuzzy set and talked about some related properties. Afterward, in 2013, Jun and Khan[6] presented the idea of cubic ideals in the semigroup. In 2013, Yager[?] started the idea of Pythagorean fuzzy set, the sum of the squares degree of membership(DOM) and degree of non-membership(DONM) has a place with the unit interval $[0,1]$. In 2019, Abbas et al.[1] introduced Cubic Pythagorean fuzzy sets. In 2019, Hussain et al.[4] started the ideas of Rough Pythagorean fuzzy ideals in the semigroup. In this paper, we introduce the properties of Pythagorean cubic ideals in semigroup.

2. PRELIMINARIES

Definition 2.1. [?] Let X be a universe of discourse, A **Pythagorean fuzzy set** (PFS) $P = \{w, \phi_p(w), \psi_p(w)/w \in X\}$ where $\phi : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ and $\psi : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ represent the DOM and DONM of the object $w \in X$ to the set P subset to the condition $0 \leq (\phi_p(w))^2 + (\psi_p(w))^2 \leq 1$ for all $w \in X$. For the sake of simplicity a PFS is denoted as $P = (\phi_p(w), \psi_p(w))$.

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3. PYTHAGOREAN CUBIC IDEAL IN SEMIGROUP

Definition 3.1. A Pythagorean cubic set(PCS) $P^c = (\phi_p^c, \psi_p^c) = \langle [\widetilde{\phi}_p, \widetilde{\psi}_p], (\phi_p, \psi_p) \rangle$ on S is known to be a Pythagorean cubic sub-semigroup(PFSS) of S . If for all $w_1, w_2 \in S$, it holds

$$\begin{aligned} \widetilde{\phi}_p(w_1w_2) &\geq \min \{ \widetilde{\phi}_p(w_1), \widetilde{\phi}_p(w_2) \} \\ \widetilde{\psi}_p(w_1w_2) &\leq \max \{ \widetilde{\psi}_p(w_1), \widetilde{\psi}_p(w_2) \} \\ \phi_p(w_1w_2) &\leq \max \{ \phi_p(w_1), \phi_p(w_2) \} \\ \psi_p(w_1w_2) &\geq \min \{ \psi_p(w_1), \psi_p(w_2) \}. \end{aligned}$$

Consider

TABLE 1. Cayley table

•	u	v	w	x	y
u	u	u	u	u	u
v	u	v	u	x	u
w	u	y	w	w	y
x	u	v	x	x	v
y	u	y	u	w	u

Example 3.2. Consider a semigroup $S = \{u, v, w, x, y\}$ with the above Cayley Table.

Define a Pythagorean cubic set(PCS) $P^c = \langle [\widetilde{\phi}_p, \widetilde{\psi}_p], (\phi_p, \psi_p) \rangle$ in S as follows.

S	$[\widetilde{\phi}_p(w_1), \widetilde{\psi}_p(w_1)]$	$(\phi_p(w_1), \psi_p(w_1))$
u	$[0.7, 0.8], [0.1, 0.2]$	$0.2, 0.7$
v	$[0.4, 0.6], [0.4, 0.5]$	$0.4, 0.5$
w	$[0.3, 0.5], [0.5, 0.6]$	$0.5, 0.3$
x	$[0.1, 0.2], [0.3, 0.5]$	$0.3, 0.2$
y	$[0.3, 0.5], [0.5, 0.6]$	$0.5, 0.3$

Thus $P^c = \langle [\widetilde{\phi}_p, \widetilde{\psi}_p], (\phi_p, \psi_p) \rangle$ is a PCSS of S .

Definition 3.3. A PCS $P^c = (\phi_{p^c}, \psi_{p^c})$ on semigroup S , is said to be a PCL (P_{LI}^c)(resp.PCR(P_{RI}^c)) ideal of S . If for all $w_1, w_2 \in S$, it holds.

$$\begin{aligned} \widetilde{\phi}_p(w_1w_2) &\geq \widetilde{\phi}_p(w_2); \phi_p(w_1w_2) \leq \phi_p(w_2) \\ \widetilde{\psi}_p(w_1w_2) &\leq \widetilde{\psi}_p(w_2); \psi_p(w_1w_2) \geq \psi_p(w_2) \end{aligned}$$

resp.right(P_{RI}^c)

$$\begin{aligned} \widetilde{\phi}_p(w_1w_2) &\geq \widetilde{\phi}_p(w_1); \phi_p(w_1w_2) \leq \phi_p(w_1) \\ \widetilde{\psi}_p(w_1w_2) &\leq \widetilde{\psi}_p(w_1); \psi_p(w_1w_2) \geq \psi_p(w_1). \end{aligned}$$

Definition 3.4. A PCS $P^c = (\phi_{p^c}, \psi_{p^c}) = \langle [\widetilde{\phi}_p, \widetilde{\psi}_p], (\phi_p, \psi_p) \rangle$ on S is called (PCI)Pythagorean cubic ideal (P_I^c)of S . If for all $w_1, w_2 \in S$, it P^c is both a left and right (PCI)Pythagorean cubic ideal of S .

$$\begin{aligned} \widetilde{\phi}_p(w_1w_2) &\geq \max \{ \widetilde{\phi}_p(w_1), \widetilde{\phi}_p(w_2) \} \\ \widetilde{\psi}_p(w_1w_2) &\leq \min \{ \widetilde{\psi}_p(w_1), \widetilde{\psi}_p(w_2) \} \\ \phi_p(w_1w_2) &\leq \min \{ \phi_p(w_1), \phi_p(w_2) \} \\ \psi_p(w_1w_2) &\geq \max \{ \psi_p(w_1), \psi_p(w_2) \}. \end{aligned}$$

Definition 3.5. A PCS $P^c = (\phi_{p^c}, \psi_{p^c}) = \langle [\widetilde{\phi}_p, \widetilde{\psi}_p], (\phi_p, \psi_p) \rangle$ on S is known to be a (PCBI)Pythagorean cubic Bi-ideal (P_{BI}^c) of S . If for all $w_1, w_2, w_3 \in S$, and satisfy.

$$\begin{aligned}\widetilde{\phi}_p(w_1 w_2 w_3) &\geq \min \left\{ \widetilde{\phi}_p(w_1), \widetilde{\phi}_p(w_3) \right\} \\ \widetilde{\psi}_p(w_1 w_2 w_3) &\leq \max \left\{ \widetilde{\psi}_p(w_1), \widetilde{\psi}_p(w_3) \right\} \\ \phi_p(w_1 w_2 w_3) &\leq \max \left\{ \phi_p(w_1), \phi_p(w_3) \right\} \\ \psi_p(w_1 w_2 w_3) &\geq \min \left\{ \psi_p(w_1), \psi_p(w_3) \right\}.\end{aligned}$$

Example 3.6. Consider a semigroup $S = \{u, v, w, x, y\}$ with the above Cayley Table.

Define a Pythagorean cubic set $P^c = \langle [\widetilde{\phi}_p, \widetilde{\psi}_p], (\phi_p, \psi_p) \rangle$ in S as follows.

S	$[\widetilde{\phi}_p(w_1), \widetilde{\psi}_p(w_1)]$	$(\phi_p(w_1), \psi_p(w_1))$
u	$[0.8, 0.9], [0.1, 0.3]$	$0.2, 0.7$
v	$[0.3, 0.5], [0.7, 0.9]$	$0.8, 0.3$
w	$[0.4, 0.6], [0.6, 0.7]$	$0.5, 0.4$
x	$[0.3, 0.5], [0.7, 0.9]$	$0.8, 0.3$
y	$[0.7, 0.8], [0.4, 0.5]$	$0.4, 0.6$

Thus $P^c = \langle [\widetilde{\phi}_p, \widetilde{\psi}_p], (\phi_p, \psi_p) \rangle$ is a PCBI of S .

Definition 3.7. A PCS $P^c = (\phi_{p^c}, \psi_{p^c}) = \langle [\widetilde{\phi}_p, \widetilde{\psi}_p], (\phi_p, \psi_p) \rangle$ on S is known to be a Pythagorean cubic interior ideal (P_{II}^c) of S . If for all $w_1, w_2, w_3 \in S$, and satisfy.

$$\begin{aligned}\widetilde{\phi}_p(w_1 w_2 w_3) &\geq \widetilde{\phi}_p(w_2) \\ \widetilde{\psi}_p(w_1 w_2 w_3) &\leq \widetilde{\psi}_p(w_2) \\ \phi_p(w_1 w_2 w_3) &\leq \phi_p(w_2) \\ \psi_p(w_1 w_2 w_3) &\geq \psi_p(w_2).\end{aligned}$$

Definition 3.8. For any non-empty subset N of a semigroup S is defined to be a structure $\chi_N = \left\{ w_1, [\widetilde{\phi}_{\chi_N}(w_1), \widetilde{\psi}_{\chi_N}(w_1)], (\phi_{\chi_N}(w_1), \psi_{\chi_N}(w_1)) \mid w_1 \in S \right\}$ which is briefly denoted by $\chi_N = \langle [\widetilde{\phi}_{\chi_N}, \widetilde{\psi}_{\chi_N}], (\phi_{\chi_N}, \psi_{\chi_N}) \rangle$ where,

$$\begin{aligned}\widetilde{\phi}_{\chi_N}(w_1) &= \begin{cases} \widetilde{1} & \text{if } x \in N \\ \widetilde{0} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} & \widetilde{\psi}_{\chi_N}(w_1) &= \begin{cases} \widetilde{0} & \text{if } x \in N \\ \widetilde{1} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \\ \phi_{\chi_N}(w_1) &= \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } x \in N \\ 1 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} & \psi_{\chi_N}(w_1) &= \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } x \in N \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}\end{aligned}$$

Theorem 3.1. Let S be a semigroup. Then,

(i) The intersection of two Pythagorean cubic sub-semigroup (PCSS) of S , is a Pythagorean cubic sub-semigroup (PCSS) of S .

(ii) The intersection of two Pythagorean cubic left (PCL)(resp. PCR)ideal of S , is PCLI (resp. PCRI) of S .

Proof. Let $P_1^c = \langle [\widetilde{\phi}_{p_1}, \widetilde{\psi}_{p_1}], (\phi_{p_1}, \psi_{p_1}) \rangle$ and $P_2^c = \langle [\widetilde{\phi}_{p_2}, \widetilde{\psi}_{p_2}], (\phi_{p_2}, \psi_{p_2}) \rangle$ be two Pythagorean cubic sub-semigroup of S . Let $w_1, w_2 \in S$.

Then,

$$\begin{aligned}(i) \left(\widetilde{\phi}_{p_1} \cap \widetilde{\phi}_{p_2} \right) (w_1, w_2) &= \min \left\{ \widetilde{\phi}_{p_1}(w_1, w_2), \widetilde{\phi}_{p_2}(w_1, w_2) \right\} \\ &\geq \min \left\{ \min \left\{ \widetilde{\phi}_{p_1}(w_1), \widetilde{\phi}_{p_1}(w_2) \right\}, \min \left\{ \widetilde{\phi}_{p_2}(w_1), \widetilde{\phi}_{p_2}(w_2) \right\} \right\}\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \min \left\{ \min \left\{ \tilde{\phi}_{p_1}(w_1), \tilde{\phi}_{p_2}(w_1) \right\}, \min \left\{ \tilde{\phi}_{p_1}(w_2), \tilde{\phi}_{p_2}(w_2) \right\} \right\} \\
 &= \min \left\{ \tilde{\phi}_{p_1} \cap \tilde{\phi}_{p_2}(w_1), \tilde{\phi}_{p_1} \cap \tilde{\phi}_{p_2}(w_2) \right\} \\
 (\tilde{\psi}_{p_1} \cup \tilde{\psi}_{p_2})(w_1, w_2) &= \max \left\{ \tilde{\psi}_{p_1}(w_1, w_2), \tilde{\psi}_{p_2}(w_1, w_2) \right\} \\
 &\leq \max \left\{ \max \left\{ \tilde{\psi}_{p_1}(w_1), \tilde{\psi}_{p_1}(w_2) \right\}, \max \left\{ \tilde{\psi}_{p_2}(w_1), \tilde{\psi}_{p_2}(w_2) \right\} \right\} \\
 &= \max \left\{ \max \left\{ \tilde{\psi}_{p_1}(w_1), \tilde{\psi}_{p_2}(w_1) \right\}, \max \left\{ \tilde{\psi}_{p_1}(w_2), \tilde{\psi}_{p_2}(w_2) \right\} \right\} \\
 &= \max \left\{ \tilde{\psi}_{p_1} \cup \tilde{\psi}_{p_2}(w_1), \tilde{\psi}_{p_1} \cup \tilde{\psi}_{p_2}(w_2) \right\} \\
 (\phi_{p_1} \cup \phi_{p_2})(w_1, w_2) &= \max \left\{ \phi_{p_1}(w_1, w_2), \phi_{p_2}(w_1, w_2) \right\} \\
 &\leq \max \left\{ \max \left\{ \phi_{p_1}(w_1), \phi_{p_1}(w_2) \right\}, \max \left\{ \phi_{p_2}(w_1), \phi_{p_2}(w_2) \right\} \right\} \\
 &= \max \left\{ \max \left\{ \phi_{p_1}(w_1), \phi_{p_2}(w_1) \right\}, \max \left\{ \phi_{p_1}(w_2), \phi_{p_2}(w_2) \right\} \right\} \\
 &= \max \left\{ \phi_{p_1} \cup \phi_{p_2}(w_1), \phi_{p_1} \cup \phi_{p_2}(w_2) \right\} \\
 (\psi_{p_1} \cap \psi_{p_2})(w_1, w_2) &= \min \left\{ \psi_{p_1}(w_1, w_2), \psi_{p_2}(w_1, w_2) \right\} \\
 &\geq \min \left\{ \min \left\{ \psi_{p_1}(w_1), \psi_{p_1}(w_2) \right\}, \min \left\{ \psi_{p_2}(w_1), \psi_{p_2}(w_2) \right\} \right\} \\
 &= \min \left\{ \min \left\{ \psi_{p_1}(w_1), \psi_{p_2}(w_1) \right\}, \min \left\{ \psi_{p_1}(w_2), \psi_{p_2}(w_2) \right\} \right\} \\
 &= \min \left\{ \psi_{p_1} \cap \psi_{p_2}(w_1), \psi_{p_1} \cap \psi_{p_2}(w_2) \right\}
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $P_1^c \cap P_2^c = \left\{ \left\langle \left(\tilde{\phi}_{p_1} \cap \tilde{\phi}_{p_2} \right), \left(\tilde{\psi}_{p_1} \cup \tilde{\psi}_{p_2} \right) \right\rangle, \left(\phi_{p_1} \cup \phi_{p_2} \right), \left(\psi_{p_1} \cap \psi_{p_2} \right) \right\}$

PCSS of S .

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{(ii)} \quad (\tilde{\phi}_{p_1} \cap \tilde{\phi}_{p_2})(w_1, w_2) &= \min \left\{ \tilde{\phi}_{p_1}(w_1, w_2), \tilde{\phi}_{p_2}(w_1, w_2) \right\} \\
 &\geq \min \left\{ \tilde{\phi}_{p_1}(w_2), \tilde{\phi}_{p_2}(w_2) \right\} \\
 &= \left(\tilde{\phi}_{p_1} \cap \tilde{\phi}_{p_2} \right)(w_2) \\
 (\tilde{\psi}_{p_1} \cup \tilde{\psi}_{p_2})(w_1, w_2) &= \max \left\{ \tilde{\psi}_{p_1}(w_1, w_2), \tilde{\psi}_{p_2}(w_1, w_2) \right\} \\
 &\leq \max \left\{ \tilde{\psi}_{p_1}(w_2), \tilde{\psi}_{p_2}(w_2) \right\} \\
 &= \left(\tilde{\psi}_{p_1} \cup \tilde{\psi}_{p_2} \right)(w_2) \\
 (\phi_{p_1} \cup \phi_{p_2})(w_1, w_2) &= \max \left\{ \phi_{p_1}(w_1, w_2), \phi_{p_2}(w_1, w_2) \right\} \\
 &\leq \max \left\{ \phi_{p_1}(w_2), \phi_{p_2}(w_2) \right\} \\
 &= \left(\phi_{p_1} \cup \phi_{p_2} \right)(w_2) \\
 (\psi_{p_1} \cap \psi_{p_2})(w_1, w_2) &= \min \left\{ \psi_{p_1}(w_1, w_2), \psi_{p_2}(w_1, w_2) \right\} \\
 &\geq \min \left\{ \psi_{p_1}(w_2), \psi_{p_2}(w_2) \right\} \\
 &= \left(\psi_{p_1} \cap \psi_{p_2} \right)(w_2).
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, (i) and (ii) $P_1^c \cap P_2^c = \left\{ \left\langle \left(\tilde{\phi}_{p_1} \cap \tilde{\phi}_{p_2} \right), \left(\tilde{\psi}_{p_1} \cup \tilde{\psi}_{p_2} \right) \right\rangle, \left(\phi_{p_1} \cup \phi_{p_2} \right), \left(\psi_{p_1} \cap \psi_{p_2} \right) \right\}$ is a Pythagorean cubic left(resp. right) ideal of S .

□

Theorem 3.2. A PCS $P^c = \left\langle \left[\tilde{\phi}_p, \tilde{\psi}_p \right], \left(\phi_p, \psi_p \right) \right\rangle$ of a semigroup S is a PCBI of S , iff $\left\langle \left(\phi_p^L, \phi_p^U \right), \left(\psi_p^L, \psi_p^U \right) \right\rangle$ and $\left(\phi_p, \psi_p \right)$ are PFI of S .

Proof. Let $P^c = \left\langle \left[\tilde{\phi}_p, \tilde{\psi}_p \right], \left(\phi_p, \psi_p \right) \right\rangle$ be a PFBI(Pythagorean cubic bi-ideal) of S , for any $w_1, w_2 \in S$.

Then, we have membership

$$\begin{aligned}
 \left[\phi_p^L(w_1 w_2), \phi_p^U(w_1 w_2) \right] &= \tilde{\phi}_p(w_1 w_2) \\
 &\geq \min \left\{ \tilde{\phi}_p(w_1), \tilde{\phi}_p(w_2) \right\}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \min \{ [\phi_p^L(w_1), \phi_p^U(w_1)], [\phi_p^L(w_2), \phi_p^U(w_2)] \} \\
&= \min \{ [\phi_p^L(w_1), \phi_p^L(w_2)], [\phi_p^U(w_1), \phi_p^U(w_2)] \}.
\end{aligned}$$

It follows that $\phi_p^L(w_1w_2) \geq \min \{ \phi_p^L(w_1), \phi_p^L(w_2) \}$ and $\phi_p^U(w_1w_2) \geq \min \{ \phi_p^U(w_1), \phi_p^U(w_2) \}$ and non-membership

$$\begin{aligned}
[\psi_p^L(w_1w_2), \psi_p^U(w_1w_2)] &= \tilde{\psi}_p(w_1w_2) \\
&\leq \max \{ \tilde{\psi}_p(w_1), \tilde{\psi}_p(w_2) \} \\
&= \max \{ [\psi_p^L(w_1), \psi_p^U(w_1)], [\psi_p^L(w_2), \psi_p^U(w_2)] \} \\
&= \max \{ [\psi_p^L(w_1), \psi_p^L(w_2)], [\psi_p^U(w_1), \psi_p^U(w_2)] \}.
\end{aligned}$$

It follows that $\psi_p^L(w_1w_2) \leq \max \{ \psi_p^L(w_1), \psi_p^L(w_2) \}$ and $\psi_p^U(w_1w_2) \leq \max \{ \psi_p^U(w_1), \psi_p^U(w_2) \}$

Clearly, $\phi_p(w_1w_2) \leq \max \{ \phi_p(w_1), \phi_p(w_2) \}$ and $\psi_p(w_1w_2) \geq \min \{ \psi_p(w_1), \psi_p(w_2) \}$.

Therefore, $P = \langle (\phi_p^L, \phi_p^U), (\psi_p^L, \psi_p^U) \rangle$ and (ϕ_p, ψ_p) are Pythagorean fuzzy ideal of S .

Conversely, suppose that $([\phi_p^L, \phi_p^U], [\psi_p^L, \psi_p^U])$ and (ϕ_p, ψ_p) are Pythagorean fuzzy ideal of S , let $w_1, w_2 \in S$.

$$\begin{aligned}
\tilde{\phi}_p(w_1w_2) &= [\phi_p^L(w_1w_2), \phi_p^U(w_1w_2)] \\
&\geq [\min \{ \phi_p^L(w_1), \phi_p^L(w_2) \}, \min \{ \phi_p^U(w_1), \phi_p^U(w_2) \}] \\
&= \min \{ [\phi_p^L(w_1), \phi_p^U(w_1)], [\phi_p^L(w_2), \phi_p^U(w_2)] \} \\
&= \min \{ \tilde{\phi}_p(w_1), \tilde{\phi}_p(w_2) \}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\tilde{\psi}_p(w_1w_2) &= [\psi_p^L(w_1w_2), \psi_p^U(w_1w_2)] \\
&\leq [\max \{ \psi_p^L(w_1), \psi_p^L(w_2) \}, \max \{ \psi_p^U(w_1), \psi_p^U(w_2) \}] \\
&= \max \{ [\psi_p^L(w_1), \psi_p^U(w_1)], [\psi_p^L(w_2), \psi_p^U(w_2)] \} \\
&= \max \{ \tilde{\psi}_p(w_1), \tilde{\psi}_p(w_2) \}.
\end{aligned}$$

Clearly, $\phi_p(w_1w_2) \leq \max \{ \phi_p(w_1), \phi_p(w_2) \}$ and $\psi_p(w_1w_2) \geq \min \{ \psi_p(w_1), \psi_p(w_2) \}$

$P^c = \langle [\tilde{\phi}_p, \tilde{\psi}_p], (\phi_p, \psi_p) \rangle$ is a Pythagorean cubic sub-semigroup of S .

$$\begin{aligned}
\tilde{\phi}_p(w_1w_2w_3) &= [\phi_p^L(w_1w_2w_3), \phi_p^U(w_1w_2w_3)] \\
&\geq [\min \{ \phi_p^L(w_1), \phi_p^L(w_3) \}, \min \{ \phi_p^U(w_1), \phi_p^U(w_3) \}] \\
&= \min \{ [\phi_p^L(w_1), \phi_p^U(w_1)], [\phi_p^L(w_3), \phi_p^U(w_3)] \} \\
&= \min \{ \tilde{\phi}_p(w_1), \tilde{\phi}_p(w_3) \}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\tilde{\psi}_p(w_1w_2w_3) &= [\psi_p^L(w_1w_2w_3), \psi_p^U(w_1w_2w_3)] \\
&\leq [\max \{ \psi_p^L(w_1), \psi_p^L(w_3) \}, \max \{ \psi_p^U(w_1), \psi_p^U(w_3) \}] \\
&= \max \{ [\psi_p^L(w_1), \psi_p^U(w_1)], [\psi_p^L(w_3), \psi_p^U(w_3)] \} \\
&= \max \{ \tilde{\psi}_p(w_1), \tilde{\psi}_p(w_3) \}.
\end{aligned}$$

Clearly, $\phi_p(w_1w_2w_3) \leq \max \{ \phi_p(w_1), \phi_p(w_3) \}$ and $\psi_p(w_1w_2w_3) \geq \min \{ \psi_p(w_1), \psi_p(w_3) \}$

$P^c = \langle [\tilde{\phi}_p, \tilde{\psi}_p], (\phi_p, \psi_p) \rangle$ is a Pythagorean cubic bi-ideal of S . \square

Theorem 3.3. *If $\{P_i\}_{i \in I}$ is a family of Pythagorean cubic bi-ideal of a semigroup S . Then*

$\cap P_i$ *is a Pythagorean cubic bi-ideal of S . Where $\cap P_i = ((\cap \tilde{\phi}_{p_i}, \cup \tilde{\psi}_{p_i}), (\cup \phi_{p_i}, \cap \psi_{p_i}))$.*

$$\cap (\tilde{\phi}_{p_i}) = \inf \left\{ (\tilde{\phi}_{p_i})(w_1) / i \in I, w_1 \in S \right\},$$

$$\cup (\tilde{\psi}_{p_i}) = \sup \left\{ (\tilde{\psi}_{p_i})(w_1) / i \in I, w_1 \in S \right\},$$

$$\cup (\phi_{p_i}) = \sup \{ (\phi_{p_i})(w_1) / i \in I, w_1 \in S \},$$

$$\cap (\psi_{p_i}) = \inf \{ (\psi_{p_i})(w_1) / i \in I, w_1 \in S \} \text{ and } i \in I \text{ is any index set.}$$

Proof. Since $P_i = \left\langle \left[\tilde{\phi}_{p_i}, \tilde{\psi}_{p_i} \right], (\phi_{p_i}, \psi_{p_i}) \mid i \in I \right\rangle$ is a family of Pythagorean cubic bi-ideals of S . Let $w_1, w_2, w_3 \in S$.

$$\begin{aligned} \cap \tilde{\phi}_{p_i}(w_1, w_2) &= \inf \left\{ \tilde{\phi}_{p_i}(w_1, w_2) / i \in I, w_1, w_2 \in S \right\} \\ &\geq \inf \left\{ \min \left\{ \tilde{\phi}_{p_i}(w_1), \tilde{\phi}_{p_i}(w_2) \right\} \right\} \\ &= \min \left\{ \inf \left(\tilde{\phi}_{p_i}(w_1) \right), \inf \left(\tilde{\phi}_{p_i}(w_2) \right) \right\} \\ &= \min \left\{ \cap \tilde{\phi}_{p_i}(w_1), \cap \tilde{\phi}_{p_i}(w_2) \right\} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \cup \tilde{\psi}_{p_i}(w_1 w_2) &= \sup \left\{ \tilde{\psi}_{p_i}(w_1 w_2) / i \in I, w_1, w_2 \in S \right\} \\ &\leq \sup \left\{ \max \left\{ \tilde{\psi}_{p_i}(w_1), \tilde{\psi}_{p_i}(w_2) \right\} \right\} \\ &= \max \left\{ \sup \left(\tilde{\psi}_{p_i}(w_1) \right), \sup \left(\tilde{\psi}_{p_i}(w_2) \right) \right\} \\ &= \max \left\{ \cup \tilde{\psi}_{p_i}(w_1), \cup \tilde{\psi}_{p_i}(w_2) \right\} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \cup \phi_{p_i}(w_1 w_2) &= \sup \left\{ \phi_{p_i}(w_1 w_2) / i \in I, w_1, w_2 \in S \right\} \\ &\leq \sup \left\{ \max \left\{ \phi_{p_i}(w_1), \phi_{p_i}(w_2) \right\} \right\} \\ &= \max \left\{ \sup \left(\phi_{p_i}(w_1) \right), \sup \left(\phi_{p_i}(w_2) \right) \right\} \\ &= \max \left\{ \cup \phi_{p_i}(w_1), \cup \phi_{p_i}(w_2) \right\} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \cap \psi_{p_i}(w_1 w_2) &= \inf \left\{ \psi_{p_i}(w_1 w_2) / i \in I, w_1, w_2 \in S \right\} \\ &\geq \inf \left\{ \min \left\{ \psi_{p_i}(w_1), \psi_{p_i}(w_2) \right\} \right\} \\ &= \min \left\{ \inf \left(\psi_{p_i}(w_1) \right), \inf \left(\psi_{p_i}(w_2) \right) \right\} \\ &= \min \left\{ \cap \psi_{p_i}(w_1), \cap \psi_{p_i}(w_2) \right\}. \end{aligned}$$

Hence, $\cap P_i^c = \left(\left(\cap \tilde{\phi}_{p_i}, \cup \tilde{\psi}_{p_i} \right), \left(\cup \phi_{p_i}, \cap \psi_{p_i} \right) \right)$ is a Pythagorean cubic sub-semigroup of S .

$$\begin{aligned} \cap \tilde{\phi}_{p_i}(w_1 w_2 w_3) &= \inf \left\{ \tilde{\phi}_{p_i}(w_1, w_2 w_3) / i \in I, w_1, w_2, w_3 \in S \right\} \\ &\geq \inf \left\{ \min \left\{ \tilde{\phi}_{p_i}(w_1), \tilde{\phi}_{p_i}(w_3) \right\} \right\} \\ &= \min \left\{ \inf \left(\tilde{\phi}_{p_i}(w_1) \right), \inf \left(\tilde{\phi}_{p_i}(w_3) \right) \right\} \\ &= \min \left\{ \cap \tilde{\phi}_{p_i}(w_1), \cap \tilde{\phi}_{p_i}(w_3) \right\} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \cup \tilde{\psi}_{p_i}(w_1 w_2 w_3) &= \sup \left\{ \tilde{\psi}_{p_i}(w_1 w_2 w_3) / i \in I, w_1, w_2, w_3 \in S \right\} \\ &\leq \sup \left\{ \max \left\{ \tilde{\psi}_{p_i}(w_1), \tilde{\psi}_{p_i}(w_3) \right\} \right\} \\ &= \max \left\{ \sup \left(\tilde{\psi}_{p_i}(w_1) \right), \sup \left(\tilde{\psi}_{p_i}(w_3) \right) \right\} \\ &= \max \left\{ \cup \tilde{\psi}_{p_i}(w_1), \cup \tilde{\psi}_{p_i}(w_3) \right\} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \cup \phi_{p_i}(w_1 w_2 w_3) &= \sup \left\{ \phi_{p_i}(w_1 w_2 w_3) / i \in I, w_1, w_2, w_3 \in S \right\} \\ &\leq \sup \left\{ \max \left\{ \phi_{p_i}(w_1), \phi_{p_i}(w_3) \right\} \right\} \\ &= \max \left\{ \sup \left(\phi_{p_i}(w_1) \right), \sup \left(\phi_{p_i}(w_3) \right) \right\} \\ &= \max \left\{ \cup \phi_{p_i}(w_1), \cup \phi_{p_i}(w_3) \right\} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \cap \psi_{p_i}(w_1 w_2 w_3) &= \inf \left\{ \psi_{p_i}(w_1 w_2 w_3) / i \in I, w_1, w_2, w_3 \in S \right\} \\ &\geq \inf \left\{ \min \left\{ \psi_{p_i}(w_1), \psi_{p_i}(w_3) \right\} \right\} \\ &= \min \left\{ \inf \left(\psi_{p_i}(w_1) \right), \inf \left(\psi_{p_i}(w_3) \right) \right\} \\ &= \min \left\{ \cap \psi_{p_i}(w_1), \cap \psi_{p_i}(w_3) \right\}. \end{aligned}$$

Hence, $\cap P_i^c = \left(\left(\cap \tilde{\phi}_{p_i}, \cup \tilde{\psi}_{p_i} \right), \left(\cup \phi_{p_i}, \cap \psi_{p_i} \right) \right)$ is a PCBI of S . \square

Theorem 3.4. *Let N be any non-empty subset of a semigroup S . Then N is a bi-ideal of S , iff the characteristic Pythagorean cubic set $\chi_N = \langle [\tilde{\phi}_{p_{\chi_N}}, \tilde{\psi}_{p_{\chi_N}}], (\phi_{p_{\chi_N}}, \psi_{p_{\chi_N}}) \rangle$ is PCBI of S .*

Proof. Assume that N is a bi-ideal of S . Let $w_1, w_2, w_3 \in S$. Suppose that $\tilde{\phi}_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_1 w_2) < \min \{ \tilde{\phi}_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_1), \tilde{\phi}_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_2) \}$ and $\tilde{\psi}_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_1 w_2) > \max \{ \tilde{\psi}_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_1), \tilde{\psi}_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_2) \}$ it follows that $\tilde{\phi}_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_1 w_2) = 0, \min \{ \tilde{\phi}_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_1), \tilde{\phi}_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_2) \} = 1, \tilde{\psi}_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_1 w_2) = 1,$
 $\max \{ \tilde{\psi}_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_1), \tilde{\psi}_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_2) \} = 0, \phi_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_1 w_2) > \max \{ \phi_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_1), \phi_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_2) \}$ and
 $\psi_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_1 w_2) < \min \{ \psi_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_1), \psi_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_2) \}$ it follows that $\phi_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_1 w_2) = 1,$
 $\max \{ \phi_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_1), \phi_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_2) \} = 0, \psi_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_1 w_2) = 0, \min \{ \psi_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_1), \psi_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_2) \} = 1.$
 This implies that $w_1, w_2 \in N$ by $w_1, w_2 \notin N$ a contradiction to N . So $\tilde{\phi}_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_1 w_2) \geq$
 $\min \{ \tilde{\phi}_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_1), \tilde{\phi}_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_2) \}, \tilde{\psi}_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_1 w_2) \leq \max \{ \tilde{\psi}_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_1), \tilde{\psi}_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_2) \}, \phi_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_1 w_2) \leq$
 $\max \{ \phi_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_1), \phi_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_2) \}$ and $\psi_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_1 w_2) \geq \min \{ \psi_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_1), \psi_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_2) \}.$

Suppose that $\tilde{\phi}_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_1 w_2 w_3) < \min \{ \tilde{\phi}_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_1), \tilde{\phi}_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_3) \}$ and

$\tilde{\psi}_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_1 w_2 w_3) > \max \{ \tilde{\psi}_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_1), \tilde{\psi}_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_3) \}$ it follows that

$\tilde{\phi}_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_1 w_2 w_3) = 0, \min \{ \tilde{\phi}_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_1), \tilde{\phi}_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_3) \} = 1,$

$\tilde{\psi}_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_1 w_2 w_3) = 1, \max \{ \tilde{\psi}_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_1), \tilde{\psi}_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_3) \} = 0,$

$\phi_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_1 w_2 w_3) > \max \{ \phi_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_1), \phi_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_3) \}$

and $\psi_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_1 w_2 w_3) < \min \{ \psi_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_1), \psi_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_3) \}$ it follows that

$\phi_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_1 w_2 w_3) = 1, \max \{ \phi_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_1), \phi_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_3) \} = 0,$

$\psi_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_1 w_2 w_3) = 0, \min \{ \psi_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_1), \psi_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_3) \} = 1.$

This implies that $w_1, w_2, w_3 \in N$ by $w_1, w_2, w_3 \notin N$ a contradiction to N .

So $\tilde{\phi}_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_1 w_2 w_3) \geq \min \{ \tilde{\phi}_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_1), \tilde{\phi}_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_3) \},$

$\tilde{\psi}_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_1 w_2 w_3) \leq \max \{ \tilde{\psi}_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_1), \tilde{\psi}_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_3) \},$

$\phi_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_1 w_2 w_3) \leq \max \{ \phi_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_1), \phi_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_3) \}$

and $\psi_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_1 w_2 w_3) \geq \min \{ \psi_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_1), \psi_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_3) \}.$

This shows that χ_N is a Pythagorean cubic bi-ideal of S .

Conversely, $\chi_N = \langle [\tilde{\phi}_{p_{\chi_N}}, \tilde{\psi}_{p_{\chi_N}}], (\phi_{p_{\chi_N}}, \psi_{p_{\chi_N}}) \rangle$ is PCBI of S for any subset N of S .

Let $w_1, w_2 \in N$ then $\tilde{\phi}_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_1) = \tilde{\phi}_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_2) = \tilde{1}, \tilde{\psi}_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_1) = \tilde{\psi}_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_2) = \tilde{0}$ and
 $\phi_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_1) = \phi_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_2) = \tilde{0}$ and $\psi_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_1) = \psi_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_2) = \tilde{1}$ since χ_N is a PCBI of S .

$\tilde{\phi}_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_1 w_2) \geq \min \{ \tilde{\phi}_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_1), \tilde{\phi}_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_2) \} \geq \min \{ \tilde{1}, \tilde{1} \} = \tilde{1},$

$\tilde{\psi}_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_1 w_2) \leq \max \{ \tilde{\psi}_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_1), \tilde{\psi}_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_2) \} \leq \max \{ \tilde{0}, \tilde{0} \} = \tilde{0},$

$\phi_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_1 w_2) \leq \max \{ \phi_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_1), \phi_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_2) \} \leq \max \{ \tilde{0}, \tilde{0} \} = \tilde{0}$

and $\psi_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_1 w_2) \geq \min \{ \psi_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_1), \psi_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_2) \} \geq \min \{ \tilde{1}, \tilde{1} \} = \tilde{1}.$

This implies that $w_1 w_2 \in N$.

Let $w_1, w_2 w_3 \in N$ then $\tilde{\phi}_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_1) = \tilde{\phi}_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_2) = \tilde{\phi}_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_3) = \tilde{1}, \tilde{\psi}_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_1) =$
 $\tilde{\psi}_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_2) = \tilde{\psi}_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_3) = \tilde{0}$ and $\phi_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_1) = \phi_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_2) = \phi_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_3) = \tilde{0}$ and

$\psi_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_1) = \psi_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_2) = \psi_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_3) = \tilde{1}$ since χ_N is a PCBI of S . $\tilde{\phi}_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_1 w_2 w_3) \geq$

$\min \{ \tilde{\phi}_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_1), \tilde{\phi}_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_3) \} \geq \min \{ \tilde{1}, \tilde{1} \} = \tilde{1}, \tilde{\psi}_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_1 w_2 w_3) \leq \max \{ \tilde{\psi}_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_1), \tilde{\psi}_{p_{\chi_N}}(w_3) \} \leq$

$max\{\tilde{0}, \tilde{0}\} = \tilde{0}$,
 $\phi_{p\chi_N}(w_1w_2w_3) \leq max\{\phi_{p\chi_N}(w_1), \phi_{p\chi_N}(w_3)\} \leq max\{\tilde{0}, \tilde{0}\} = \tilde{0}$ and $\psi_{p\chi_N}(w_1w_2w_3) \geq min\{\psi_{p\chi_N}(w_1), \psi_{p\chi_N}(w_3)\} \geq min\{\tilde{1}, \tilde{1}\} = \tilde{1}$. Which implies that $w_1w_2 \in N$.
Hence N is a bi- ideal of S . □

Theorem 3.5. *If $\{P_i\}_{i \in I}$ is a family of Pythagorean cubic interior ideal of a semigroup S .*

Then $\cap P_i$ is a Pythagorean cubic interior ideal of S . Where $\cap P_i = \left(\left(\cap \tilde{\phi}_{p_i}, \cup \tilde{\psi}_{p_i} \right), \left(\cup \phi_{p_i}, \cap \psi_{p_i} \right) \right)$.

$$\begin{aligned} \cap \left(\tilde{\phi}_{p_i} \right) &= inf \left\{ \left(\tilde{\phi}_{p_i} \right) (w_1) / i \in I, w_1 \in S \right\}, \\ \cup \left(\tilde{\psi}_{p_i} \right) &= sup \left\{ \left(\tilde{\psi}_{p_i} \right) (w_1) / i \in I, w_1 \in S \right\}, \\ \cup \left(\phi_{p_i} \right) &= sup \left\{ \left(\phi_{p_i} \right) (w_1) / i \in I, w_1 \in S \right\}, \\ \cap \left(\psi_{p_i} \right) &= inf \left\{ \left(\psi_{p_i} \right) (w_1) / i \in I, w_1 \in S \right\} \text{ and } i \in I \text{ is any index set.} \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 3.6. *Let N be any non-empty subset of a semigroup S . Then N is a interior ideal of S , iff the characteristic Pythagorean cubic set $\chi_N = \left\langle \left[\tilde{\phi}_{p\chi_N}, \tilde{\psi}_{p\chi_N} \right], \left(\phi_{p\chi_N}, \psi_{p\chi_N} \right) \right\rangle$ is PCII of S .*

4. HOMOMORPHISM OF PYTHAGOREAN CUBIC IDEAL IN SEMIGROUP

Let R and T be two non-empty sets of semigroup S . A mapping $f : R \rightarrow T$ is called a homomorphism if $f(rt) = f(r)f(t) \forall r, t \in R$.

Definition 4.1. Let f be a mapping from a set R to a set T and $P^c = \left\langle \left[\tilde{\phi}_p, \tilde{\psi}_p \right], \left(\phi_p, \psi_p \right) \right\rangle$ be a Pythagorean cubic set R the the image of R (i.e.,) $f(P^c) = (f(\tilde{\phi}_p), f(\tilde{\psi}_p), f(\phi_p), f(\psi_p))$ is a Pythagorean cubic set of T is defined by

$$f(P^c)(r) = \begin{cases} f(\tilde{\phi}_p)(r) = \begin{cases} \sup_{t \in f^{-1}(r)} (\tilde{\phi}_p)(t), & \text{if } f^{-1}(r) = 0 \\ [0, 0] & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \\ f(\tilde{\psi}_p)(r) = \begin{cases} \inf_{t \in f^{-1}(r)} (\tilde{\psi}_p)(t), & \text{if } f^{-1}(r) = 0 \\ [1, 1] & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \\ f(\phi_p)(r) = \begin{cases} \inf_{t \in f^{-1}(r)} (\phi_p)(t), & \text{if } f^{-1}(r) = 0 \\ [1, 1] & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \\ f(\psi_p)(r) = \begin{cases} \sup_{t \in f^{-1}(r)} (\psi_p)(t), & \text{if } f^{-1}(r) = 0 \\ [0, 0] & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \end{cases}$$

Let f be a mapping from a set R to T and $P^c = \left\langle \left[\tilde{\phi}_p, \tilde{\psi}_p \right], \left(\phi_p, \psi_p \right) \right\rangle$ be a Pythagorean cubic set of T then the pre image of T (i.e.,) $f^{-1}(P^c) = \left\{ (f^{-1}(\tilde{\phi}_p), f^{-1}(\tilde{\psi}_p)), (f^{-1}(\phi_p), f^{-1}(\psi_p)) \right\}$ is an Pythagorean cubic set of R is defined as

$$f^{-1}(P^c)(r) = \begin{cases} f^{-1}(\tilde{\phi}_p)(r) = \tilde{\phi}_p(f(r)) \\ f^{-1}(\tilde{\psi}_p)(r) = \tilde{\psi}_p(f(r)) \\ f^{-1}(\phi_p)(r) = \phi_p(f(r)) \\ f^{-1}(\psi_p)(r) = \psi_p(f(r)) \end{cases}$$

Theorem 4.1. *Let R, T be a semigroups, $f : R \rightarrow T$ be a homomorphism of semigroups.*

(a) *If $P^c = \langle [\tilde{\phi}_p, \tilde{\psi}_p], (\phi_p, \psi_p) \rangle$ is a Pythagorean cubic sub-semigroup of T the the preimage $f^{-1}(P^c) = (f^{-1}(\tilde{\phi}_p), f^{-1}(\tilde{\psi}_p), f^{-1}(\phi_p), f^{-1}(\psi_p))$ is a Pythagorean cubic sub-semigroup of R .*

(b) *If $P^c = \langle [\tilde{\phi}_p, \tilde{\psi}_p], (\phi_p, \psi_p) \rangle$ is a Pythagorean cubic left (resp. right) ideal of T the the preimage $f^{-1}(P^c) = (f^{-1}(\tilde{\phi}_p), f^{-1}(\tilde{\psi}_p), f^{-1}(\phi_p), f^{-1}(\psi_p))$ is a Pythagorean cubic left ideal (resp. right ideal) of R .*

Proof. Assume that $P^c = \langle [\tilde{\phi}_p, \tilde{\psi}_p], (\phi_p, \psi_p) \rangle$ is a Pythagorean cubic sub-semigroup of T and $r, t \in R$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{(a)(i)} \quad f^{-1}(\tilde{\phi}_p)(rt) &= \tilde{\phi}_p(f(rt)) \\
 &= \phi_p(f(r)f(t)) \\
 &\geq \min \{ \tilde{\phi}_p(f(r)), \tilde{\phi}_p(f(t)) \} \\
 &= \min \{ f^{-1}(\tilde{\phi}_p)(r), f^{-1}(\tilde{\phi}_p)(f(t)) \} \\
 \text{(ii)} \quad f^{-1}(\tilde{\psi}_p)(rt) &= \tilde{\psi}_p(f(rt)) \\
 &= \psi_p(f(r)f(t)) \\
 &\leq \max \{ \tilde{\psi}_p(f(r)), \tilde{\psi}_p(f(t)) \} \\
 &= \max \{ f^{-1}(\tilde{\psi}_p)(r), f^{-1}(\tilde{\psi}_p)(f(t)) \} \\
 \text{(iii)} \quad f^{-1}(\phi_p)(rt) &= \phi_p(f(rt)) \\
 &= \phi_p(f(r)f(t)) \\
 &\leq \max \{ \phi_p(f(r)), \phi_p(f(t)) \} \\
 &= \max \{ f^{-1}(\phi_p)(r), f^{-1}(\phi_p)(f(t)) \} \\
 \text{(iv)} \quad f^{-1}(\psi_p)(rt) &= \psi_p(f(rt)) \\
 &= \psi_p(f(r)f(t)) \\
 &\geq \min \{ \psi_p(f(r)), \psi_p(f(t)) \} \\
 &= \min \{ f^{-1}(\psi_p)(r), f^{-1}(\psi_p)(f(t)) \}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Hence, $f^{-1}(P^c) = (f^{-1}(\tilde{\phi}_p), f^{-1}(\tilde{\psi}_p), f^{-1}(\phi_p), f^{-1}(\psi_p))$ is a Pythagorean cubic sub-semigroup of R .

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{(b)(i)} \quad f^{-1}(\tilde{\phi}_p)(rt) &= \tilde{\phi}_p(f(rt)) \\
 &= \tilde{\phi}_p(f(r)f(t)) \\
 &\geq \tilde{\phi}_p(f(t)) \\
 &= f^{-1}(\tilde{\phi}_p)(f(t)) \\
 \text{(ii)} \quad f^{-1}(\tilde{\psi}_p)(rt) &= \tilde{\psi}_p(f(rt)) \\
 &= \tilde{\psi}_p(f(r)f(t)) \\
 &\leq \tilde{\psi}_p(f(t)) \\
 &= f^{-1}(\tilde{\psi}_p)(f(t)) \\
 \text{(iii)} \quad f^{-1}(\phi_p)(rt) &= \phi_p(f(rt)) \\
 &= \phi_p(f(r)f(t)) \\
 &\leq \phi_p(f(t)) \\
 &= f^{-1}(\phi_p)(f(t)) \\
 \text{(iv)} \quad f^{-1}(\psi_p)(rt) &= \psi_p(f(rt)) \\
 &= \psi_p(f(r)f(t))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\geq \psi_p(f(t)) \\ &= f^{-1}(\psi_p)(f(t)). \end{aligned}$$

Hence, $f^{-1}(P^c) = (f^{-1}(\tilde{\phi}_p), f^{-1}(\tilde{\psi}_p), f^{-1}(\phi_p), f^{-1}(\psi_p))$ is a Pythagorean cubic left(resp.right) ideal of R . \square

Theorem 4.2. *Let R, T be a semigroups, $f : R \rightarrow T$ be a homomorphism of semigroups. If $P^c = \langle [\tilde{\phi}_p, \tilde{\psi}_p], (\phi_p, \psi_p) \rangle$ is a Pythagorean cubic bi-ideal of T the the preimage $f^{-1}(P^c) = (f^{-1}(\tilde{\phi}_p), f^{-1}(\tilde{\psi}_p), f^{-1}(\phi_p), f^{-1}(\psi_p))$ is a Pythagorean cubic bi-ideal of R .*

Proof. Assume that $P^c = \langle [\tilde{\phi}_p, \tilde{\psi}_p], (\phi_p, \psi_p) \rangle$ is a Pythagorean cubic sub-semigroup of T and $a, r, t \in R$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \text{(a)(i)} \quad f^{-1}(\tilde{\phi}_p)(rat) &= \tilde{\phi}_p(f(rat)) \\ &= \tilde{\phi}_p(f(r)f(a)f(t)) \\ &\geq \min \{ \tilde{\phi}_p(f(r)), \tilde{\phi}_p(f(t)) \} \\ &= \min \{ f^{-1}(\tilde{\phi}_p)(r), f^{-1}(\tilde{\phi}_p)(f(t)) \} \\ \text{(ii)} \quad f^{-1}(\tilde{\psi}_p)(rat) &= \tilde{\psi}_p(f(rat)) \\ &= \tilde{\psi}_p(f(r)f(a)f(t)) \\ &\leq \max \{ \tilde{\psi}_p(f(r)), \tilde{\psi}_p(f(t)) \} \\ &= \max \{ f^{-1}(\tilde{\psi}_p)(r), f^{-1}(\tilde{\psi}_p)(f(t)) \} \\ \text{(iii)} \quad f^{-1}(\phi_p)(rat) &= \phi_p(f(rat)) \\ &= \phi_p(f(r)f(a)f(t)) \\ &\leq \max \{ \phi_p(f(r)), \phi_p(f(t)) \} \\ &= \max \{ f^{-1}(\phi_p)(r), f^{-1}(\phi_p)(f(t)) \} \\ \text{(iv)} \quad f^{-1}(\psi_p)(rat) &= \psi_p(f(rat)) \\ &= \psi_p(f(r)f(a)f(t)) \\ &\geq \min \{ \psi_p(f(r)), \psi_p(f(t)) \} \\ &= \min \{ f^{-1}(\psi_p)(r), f^{-1}(\psi_p)(f(t)) \}. \end{aligned}$$

Hence $f^{-1}(P^c) = (f^{-1}(\tilde{\phi}_p), f^{-1}(\tilde{\psi}_p), f^{-1}(\phi_p), f^{-1}(\psi_p))$ is a Pythagorean cubic bi-ideal of R . \square

Theorem 4.3. *Let R, T be a semigroups, $f : R \rightarrow T$ be a homomorphism of semigroups. If $P^c = \langle [\tilde{\phi}_p, \tilde{\psi}_p], (\phi_p, \psi_p) \rangle$ is a Pythagorean cubic interior ideal of T the preimage $f^{-1}(P^c) = (f^{-1}(\tilde{\phi}_p), f^{-1}(\tilde{\psi}_p), f^{-1}(\phi_p), f^{-1}(\psi_p))$ is a Pythagorean cubic interior ideal of R .*

5. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper we have obtained the union, intersection of PCI. The properties of Pythagorean cubic left(right) ideals, bi-ideals, interior ideals and sub-semigroup of semigroup.

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